

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

MASTER DEGREE IN NATURAL SCIENCES
Physics Laboratory - II

Network Analysis of Accelerating Cavities - NACav2

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1 Introduction

This document serves as the report for the NACav2 experiment, which focuses on the network analysis of accelerating cavities. The main objective of this experiment is to characterize an accelerating device commonly used in modern particle accelerators. By doing so, we aim to gain familiarity with the electrical characterization of devices operating at high frequencies, typically in the GHz range.

To achieve this goal, a training phase was carried out. This involved acquiring proficiency in using a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA), a device used for measuring various quantities, which are briefly explained in the dedicated section. Additionally, we learned data analysis strategies using MATLAB.

Initially, measurements were conducted on simple devices such as coaxial cables, filters, and directional couplers. Subsequently, we progressed to studying the fundamental component of an accelerating device: the pillbox cavity. Through these steps, we gained insights into the behavior and properties of these devices.

Finally, we successfully carried out a comprehensive characterization of a multi-cell cavity, which consists of multiple pillbox cavities assembled together. Additionally, we developed a MATLAB routine capable of monitoring the resonant frequency and quality factor of a cavity for any desired duration.

2 Scattering parameters

Understanding the physical significance of the quantities obtained from a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) is crucial. Specifically, we focus on the scattering parameters, denoted as S_{ij} .

$$S_{ij} = \frac{V_{out,i}}{V_{in,j}} \quad (1)$$

For a given electronic device, the scattering parameter S_{ij} represents the ratio of the output potential $V_{out,i}$ measured at port j to the input potential $V_{in,j}$ applied at port i . In other words, it quantifies the relationship between the input and output voltages for a specific port configuration.

By applying the superposition principle, it is indeed possible to define a vector comprising the input potentials at each port of a device. This vector can then be multiplied by a matrix composed of the scattering parameters, known as the scattering matrix. For a two-port device, the scattering matrix can be represented as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ S_{21} & S_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In the context of scattering parameters, where (b_1, b_2) represents the output vector and (a_1, a_2) represents the input vector, it is essential to remember that scattering parameters are complex numbers. The phase of a scattering parameter corresponds to the phase difference between the output and input waves, whereas the amplitude represents the ratio of their amplitudes.

When discussing the modulus of scattering parameters, it is common to express it in decibels (dB). The conversion from the linear magnitude to decibels is performed using the following formula:

$$|S_{ij}|_{db} = 20 \log_{10} (|S_{ij}|_{lin}) \quad (3)$$

Another common representation for scattering parameters is the Smith chart. The Smith chart is a graphical tool that facilitates the analysis and visualization of complex impedance values, given by $\Gamma = \frac{Z - Z_c}{Z + Z_c}$, where Z is the impedance and Z_0 the reference (typically $Z_c = 50\Omega$).

Figure 1: Smith chart conversion

In the Smith chart, each blue circle represents a real impedance value. The center of the chart corresponds to the reference impedance Z_c , while the left end represents an impedance of 0 and the right end represents an impedance of infinity. On the chart, the arcs represent the imaginary parts of the impedance. Positive arcs denote capacitance, while negative arcs indicate inductance.

3 Experimental apparatus

The experimental setup consists of two main components: the Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) and the device under test (DUT) that we aim to characterize. To analyze the DUT, we utilize the VNA as a two-port device by connecting it to the DUT using two coaxial cables. This allows us to perform measurements on two ports at a time.

The VNA provides us with comprehensive information in the form of scattering parameters as a function of frequency. This versatility enables us to focus on specific

features of interest, such as modulus or phase, facilitating a thorough analysis of each scattering parameter for the DUT. We conducted measurements on a two-port basis, capturing the complete set of scattering parameters.

It is essential to emphasize the importance of calibrating the VNA every time the instrument is powered on. This calibration compensates for the effects introduced by the coaxial cables connecting the VNA to the DUT. Without calibration, these cables could perturb the measurement output and introduce errors. With respect to uncertainties, the VNA is a highly precise and accurate instrument. Therefore, for each direct measurement, we can confidently report the presented digits without any uncertainty. The primary source of potential errors lies in the reproducibility of the measurements, as the properties of the DUT can be influenced by its surrounding environment.

4 Training part 1 - Common devices

This section introduces the initial phase of our training, where we examine commonly used devices that are not specific to accelerators. We discuss the analysis of coaxial cables, which are widely employed for wave transportation in various applications. In addition, we explore filters designed to select specific signal frequencies and directional and hybrid couplers that effectively split the signal into different ports, each contributing distinct characteristics to the output signal.

4.1 Coaxial cables

These consist of a conducting wire in the middle (copper) and a shield, separated by a dielectric which isolates the two conductors.

Figure 2: Co-axial cable

4.1.1 Transmission measurements on coaxial cable - magnitude

Transmission measurements were performed on the coaxial cable after it was connected to the two ports of the VNA. The length (L) of the connected cable was $9.3m$. The scattering parameter S_{21} was observed using the VNA as shown in Figure 3. The theoretical behavior of the scattering parameter S_{21} of the cable is given by Equation 4. Note that $\exp(-\gamma L)$ can be modified as $\exp(-\alpha L - j\beta L)$ and as $\exp(-\alpha'\sqrt{\omega}L - j\omega\tau)$.

$$S_{21}(\omega) = e^{-\gamma L} = e^{-\alpha\sqrt{\omega}L - j\omega\tau} \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: Scattering parameter S_{21} over the frequency range when the coaxial cable was connected.

Figure 4: Linear fit on $\angle S_{21}$ for a coaxial cable

This particular behavior is exploited by the following equation:

$$|S_{21}(f)|_{db} = -8.686\sqrt{2\pi}\alpha'L\sqrt{f} \quad (5)$$

Using the linearization of the plot using $\sqrt{f}$ in the x-axis and performing a linear fit, the attenuation coefficient α' was determined as $4.720(29)\frac{db\sqrt{s}}{m}$.

4.1.2 Transmission measurements on coaxial cable - phase

Then the phase was measured for the scattering parameter S_{21} , as shown in Equation 6.

$$\angle(S_{21}) = \beta L = -\omega\tau \quad (6)$$

The phase of a complex number is conventionally expressed within the range of $-\pi < \theta \leq \pi$. Consequently, for the analysis, the unwrapped phase was plotted, as illustrated in Figure 4, which avoids the jumps from $-\pi$ to π . To determine the value of the electrical delay τ , a linear fit was performed, resulting in $\tau = (26.3319 \pm 0.0016)ns$.

An alternative approach to determining this value is to introduce an electrical delay to the signal using the VNA. The delay is adjusted incrementally until a nonlinear behavior in the phase is observed, indicating the cancellation of the linear component and the selection of the correct value for τ . Using this method, the electrical delay was determined to be $26.262ns$.

Figure 5: Non linear behaviour for $\angle S_{21}$, coaxial cable

This method is relatively fast, but may not provide the highest level of accuracy. The final approach to obtaining the value of τ is through direct measurement using VNA.

Figure 6: Direct measurement of τ , coaxial cable

Based on the direct measurement using the VNA, the estimated value for τ is $\tau = 26.25ns$.

Quantity	Value
Delay measured with fictitious delay	26.262 ns
Delay measured with linear fit	(26.3319 ± 0.0016) ns
Delay measured with group delay	26.25 ns

Table 1: This table presents the obtained results for the electric delay under the three schemes.

4.1.3 Cable reflection measurements

Next, the coaxial cable is connected to port 1 of the VNA while leaving the other end open. This configuration allows us to perform reflection measurements in port 1, specifically analyzing the scattering parameter S_{11} .

Figure 7: This figure shows the magnitude of S_{11} over the frequency range. This is a zoomed version of the normal behavior.

We have another method to calculate the delay, denoted by τ , which is given by $\tau = \frac{1}{(2\Delta f)}$. Here, Δf represents the frequency difference between two consecutive peaks. To minimize procedural errors, we used markers to measure the difference for ten peaks and then divided the result by ten. For ports 1 and 2, we obtained respective values of τ as $51.296ns$ and $52.124ns$. It is important to note that these values represent the delay for light to traverse twice the length of the cable. If they are divided by 2, values that align with transmission delays will be obtained.

4.2 Attenuators

Figure 8: Attenuator 1

Figure 9: Attenuator 2

We then transition from cables to attenuators, which are two-port electrical components designed to reduce the signal amplitude. Attenuators have applications in RF and optical systems. In our study, we investigate two different attenuators. We anticipate that the phase behavior of the attenuators will resemble that of a cable. The characterization process for these devices involves measuring $|S_{11}|$ and $|S_{12}|$, as well as estimating the electrical delay τ .

4.2.1 Attenuator 1: (ATT1)

Figure 10: Magnitude of the scattering parameter S_{11} , ATT1

Figure 11: Magnitude of the scattering parameter S_{12} , ATT1

Figure 12: Magnitude of the scattering parameter S_{22} , ATT1

Figure 13: Linear fit on $\angle S_{12}$ ATT1

The electrical delay τ for the attenuator was measured to be $0.1832 \pm 0.0009 ns$. Similar to the cable, we can calculate the electrical length L_{attn1} by multiplying τ by the speed of light, giving us a value of $0.0550 \pm 0.0002 m$.

4.2.2 Attenuator 2: (ATT2)

Figure 14: Magnitude of the scattering parameter S_{11} , ATT2

Figure 15: Magnitude of the scattering parameter S_{12} , ATT 2

Figure 16: Magnitude of the scattering parameter S_{22} , ATT2

Figure 17: Linear fit on $\angle S_{12}$ ATT2

Similarly to the previous method, we can determine the length of this attenuator by performing a linear fit analysis. The measured electrical delay τ is found to be $0.0072 \pm 0.0005 ns$, which corresponds to an electrical length L_{attn2} of $0.0217 \pm 0.0002 m$ when multiplied by the speed of light.

4.3 Filters

These devices are designed to select a frequency component of the signal, kill all other components, and transmit a band around the desired frequency. For these

reasons, the quality of a filter is determined by the value of the attenuation near the resonant frequency (as close as possible to 0 dB) and the narrowness of the band.

Figure 18: Commercial band pass filter (SPARC)

Figure 19: Custom band pass filter

4.3.1 Band-pass filter (commercial)

We consider the commercial band-pass filter VBFZ-3590-S+ designed to operate within the frequency range of 3000 to 4300 MHz. The expected transmission between the two ports for an ideal device can be described by the following equation.

$$S_{21}(\omega) = e^{-j(\omega)\tau}$$

Reproducing the performance curves

The return loss and insertion loss for the commercial filter are shown here. These two quantities represent the power reflected back by the filter ($|S_{ii}|$) and the transmission from one port to the other. The filter is recommended for use within the frequency range of 3 GHz to 4 GHz by the builder, so the focus is on the frequencies around these values.

Figure 20: Insertion loss VS frequency: S_{21}

Figure 21: Return loss VS frequency: S_{11}

As expected there is a plateau near 0dB, in the frequency interval indicated by the builder, and the minimum in reflection.

Bandwidth search:

For S_{21} :

center f (GHz)	bandwidth -3dB (GHz)	top value (db)	bandwidth -25dB (GHz)
3.721	1.948	-0.8629	3.019

Table 2: Results from transmission analysis, commercial filter: center frequency, bandwidth at -3dB, value of the plateau in a linear scale, bandwidth at -25dB

Delay: The value of Group delay t_g directly measured by the instrument is $0.625ns$.

Input/output resistance:

Subsequently, we determined the input and output resistances of the band-pass filter.

Figure 22: This figure shows the plot of input resistance S_{11} over the frequency.

Figure 23: This figure shows the plot of output resistance S_{22} over the frequency.

By considering the real parts, we obtain an input resistance value of approximately 55Ω and an output resistance value of approximately 50Ω . This is consistent with the expected behavior, as devices typically have a real impedance in the vicinity of 50Ω .

4.3.2 Band-pass filter (from SPARC Low-Level RF control)

In this section, we focus on characterizing a pass band filter from SPARC. Similarly to the previous sections, we present the plot of the insertion loss, which emphasizes the frequency range where the filter exhibits minimal attenuation, as well as the return loss.

Figure 24: This figure shows the plot of magnitude of S_{21} over frequency.

For S_{21} :

center f (GHz)	bandwidth -3dB (GHz)	top value(db)	bandwidth -25dB (GHz)
2.143	0.043	-0.922	0.075

Table 3: Results from transmission analysis, custom filter: center frequency, bandwidth at -3dB, value of the plateau in a linear scale, bandwidth at -25dB

The observed characteristics indicate that this filter outperforms the commercial one. The narrower peak and closer proximity to zero attenuation demonstrate its superior performance. These results align with our expectations and also confirm that both ports exhibit similar behavior in reflection.

The phase of S_{21} :

The phase response of the filter exhibits a linear behavior within the desired operational region. By performing a linear fit on the unwrapped phase, as depicted in Figure 26, we determine the value of τ to be $25.313 \pm 0.0292ns$.

Figure 26: Linear fit of $\angle S_{21}$ over frequency

Figure 25: Overlapping $|S_{11}|$ and $|S_{22}|$ in the same plot, we compare the reflection parameters.

4.4 Couplers

4.4.1 20-dB Directional coupler:

Figure 27: 20-DB Directional coupler

The directional coupler used for measurement is the **Mini-Circuits ZX30-20-20BD-S+**. Taking one port as an input, the coupler can have one port where the signal is transmitted, ideally, not perturbed, and one coupled in which a small portion of the signal is taken. In this way, it is possible to characterize the signal without destroying it. Can also have one isolated port in which the signal should not pass at all. We evaluated its insertion loss, return loss, coupling, and directivity within the frequency range specified in the datasheet: $(0.5; 2)GHz$. The ports are labeled as follows; Port 1 is referred to as "out" in the datasheet, whereas Port 2 is referred to as "in" in the datasheet. Similarly, Port 3 is named to as "couple" in the datasheet.

Figure 28: This figure shows the plot of the magnitude of S_{21} over frequency.

Figure 29: Overlapping $|S_{11}|$, $|S_{22}|$ and $|S_{33}|$ in the same plot, we compare the reflection parameters.

Upon examining the datasheet, it becomes evident that only port 3 exhibits an incorrect return loss. Despite repeated measurements and varying VNA port configurations, the results consistently show the same outcome. Therefore, it can be concluded that port 3 is not functioning as intended.

Coupling, Isolation, and directivity

Performing the measurements, we discovered that Port 2 is coupled with 3. Figures 30, 31, 32 show the amplitude of the transmission parameter for these two ports.

Figure 30: Coupling

Figure 31: Isolation

Figure 32: Directivity

The observed plot deviates from the expected behavior, and a possible explanation for this discrepancy could be attributed to the incorrect behavior exhibited by

port 3. As indicated earlier, port 3 has already displayed an erroneous response in the frequency range where the coupler is intended to operate.

4.4.2 90-Degree Hybrid Coupler:

Figure 33: 90-Degree Hybrid coupler

This is a four-port device that evenly divides an input signal into two paths while introducing a phase shift of 90 degrees between them. This device operates within the frequency range of $2GHz$ to $3GHz$. The ports are related in the same way as the directional coupler.

Coupling(C):

The measurement of coupling is performed between the two input ports (1 and 2) and the output ports (3 and 4). Each input port is coupled with both output ports.

Figure 34: Coupling between port 1 and output ports

Figure 35: Isolation of both input ports

Isolation(I):

The isolation is between the two input ports (1 and 2), and the two output ports 3 and 4.

Phase measurement:

The device produces two output signals with a phase difference of 90 degrees. This phase shift between the output signals is a characteristic feature of the device.

Figure 36: As it should be, the phase difference is around $\pi/2$

4.5 Strip-line Beam Position Monitor (BPM)

Figure 37: Beam position monitor

Figure 38: View of the striplines

This device is designed for beam position measurement within a vacuum pipe of an accelerator. It consists of four strips that detect the signals from the beam, allowing the position to be determined by analyzing the difference in signals between two opposite strips. The schematic representation of this setup is shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Schematic circuit for each strip

We anticipate that when a signal is applied to the connector, it will predominantly be reflected back due to the presence of a short circuit. In an ideal scenario, we would only expect attenuation caused by the current flowing through a 50Ω resistor. This device is intended for use at approximately 500 MHz frequency, so our measurements were concentrated around this value with a frequency span of 150 MHz.

Reflections

Smith charts are presented for every port, as shown in Figures 40, 41, 42, and 43.

Figure 40: Smith chart for Port 1

Figure 41: Smith chart for Port 2

Figure 42: Smith chart for Port 3

Figure 43: Smith chart for Port 4

According to the provided scheme, we observe that the real part of the impedance is nearly zero, which aligns with our expectations as we anticipate a significant portion of the signal to be reflected back.

Group Delay

Regarding the group delay, we conducted measurements in reflection by analyzing the slope of the unwrapped phase.

Figure 44: Linear fit for $\angle S_{11}$ for Port 1

Figure 45: Linear fit for $\angle S_{21}$ for Port 2

τ_1	τ_2	τ_3	τ_4
1.25576($\pm$)0.00041ns	1.18712($\pm$)0.00045ns	1.17022($\pm$)0.00049ns	1.23141($\pm$)0.00045ns

Table 4: Measured group delays for different ports

Figure 46: Linear fit for $\angle S_{21}$ for Port 3

Figure 47: Linear fit for $\angle S_{21}$ for Port 4

It is noteworthy to observe that the phase approaches π as the frequency tends towards zero. This behavior is expected as the signal is being reflected back to the opposite direction of propagation due to the short circuit. Below are the obtained values for the electrical delay:

Cross Talks

This serves as an indicator of the signal transfer between adjacent strips in the BPM. In an ideal BPM, the signal in each strip should be independent of the signals in other strips. The results we obtained align with this expectation, suggesting that the signals in the different strips are effectively isolated from each other.

Figure 48: Transmission between Ports 1 and 3

Figure 49: Transmission between Ports 1 and 4

Figure 50: Transmission between Ports 2 and 3

Figure 51: Transmission between Ports 2 and 4

Additionally, it can be observed that there is a minimum value near 500 MHz, which corresponds to the frequency at which the device is intended to operate.

5 Training part 2, Pillbox cavities

A pillbox cavity exhibits cylindrical symmetry and serves as an accelerating cavity, wherein the electric and magnetic fields resonate at specific frequencies for each mode, corresponding to distinct solutions of Maxwell's equations. The resonant frequency, denoted as f_0 , is associated with the cavity. Additionally, the quality factor, represented as Q_0 , defines the ratio between the energy stored in the electromagnetic field and the dissipated power. It is given by the equation $Q_0 = \frac{f_0}{\Delta f_{3Db}} = \frac{f_0 E_c E_m}{2\pi P_{diss}}$, which also relates to the bandwidth. The wave is introduced into the cavity using an antenna, with a coupling factor denoted as $\beta = \frac{P_{ext}}{P_{diss}}$, where P_{ext} represents the power input. Lastly, the loaded quality factor denoted as Q_l , is defined as $Q_l = \frac{Q_0}{1+\beta}$. The characterization of a cavity involves estimating these parameters.

5.1 Transmission measurements

Theoretically, we expect the following behavior for the amplitude and the phase for the scattering parameters.

$$S_{12}(f) = \frac{S_{12}(f_0)}{1 + jQ_l\delta} \quad (7)$$

$$|S_{12}(f)| = \frac{|S_{12}(f_0)|}{\sqrt{1 + Q_l^2\delta^2}} \quad (8)$$

Figure 52: Pillbox cavity

$$\angle S_{12} = \tan^{-1}(-Q_t \delta) \simeq -Q_t \delta \quad (9)$$

$$\delta = \frac{f}{f_0} - \frac{f_0}{f} \quad (10)$$

5.1.1 TM_{010} mode

This mode for its resonant frequency and the transverse magnetic configuration (TM), which leads to a longitudinal E field, is typically used as the accelerator one.

The magnitude measurement of this mode, obtained using the VNA, is shown in Figure 53.

Figure 53: The peak is a little bit shifted from the expected frequency

The observed values for the resonant frequency and quality factor of this mode are $f_0 = 1.91248GHz$ and $Q = 9214.5$, respectively, obtained directly from the VNA measurements. The phase measurement of this mode, obtained using the VNA, is shown in Figure 54.

Figure 54: Phase of S_{12}

Figure 55: linear fit around f_0 .

From the linear fit performed on the phase data, we obtained the following value for the quality factor (Q factor):

$$Q_l = 9217.31(35) \quad (11)$$

It is important to consider that phase measurements are more susceptible to systematic errors, which could contribute to the inconsistency, for example, due to the fact of us choosing the interval in which there is the linear behavior.

5.1.2 Higher order modes of the pillbox

Table 5 presents the observed values for f_0 and Q of the modes at higher frequency.

Mode	$f_{0_{amp}}(GHz)$	Q_{amp}	Q_L
TM_{110}	3.04855	12499	12494.37(69)
TM_{020}	4.38835	3272.4	3349.752(39)
TM_{120}	5.57905	2772	2867.385(56)
Missing Mode 1	3.98867	6429.2	6496.86(31)
Missing Mode 2	5.61160	1244.2	1245.34(42)

Table 5: This table summarizes the observed higher-order modes and their respective resonant frequencies and loaded Q factors.

5.2 Reflection measurements

In this section, we analyzed an RF cavity's reflection, where the second port is left open, using different methods: analysis of the impedance in dB (for f_0 and Q_0), measurements of the SWR at the resonant frequency (for β), linear fit of the phase (for Q_0), non-linear fit of the amplitude. All of these procedures are performed specifically for the first mode of the cavity, known as TM_{010} . The connected port is called port 1.

5.2.1 Relevant formula

$$S_{11} = \frac{\beta - 1 - jQ_0\delta}{\beta - 1 - jQ_0\delta} \quad (12)$$

the impedance of the cavity, $Z_0 = 50\Omega$

$$Z_{Cav} = \frac{\beta Z_0}{1 + jQ_0\delta} \quad (13)$$

$$\angle S_{11} = -\arctan \frac{2\beta Q_0\delta}{\beta^2 - 1 - (Q_0\delta)^2} \quad (14)$$

for $f \simeq f_0$:

$$\angle S_{11} \simeq \frac{4\beta}{1 - \beta^2} Q_0 \frac{f - f_0}{f_0} \quad (15)$$

Standing wave ratio SWR :

$$SWR(f) = \frac{1 + |S_{11}(f)|}{1 - |S_{11}(f)|} \quad (16)$$

If $\beta > 1$ (over coupled):

$$\beta = SWR(f_0) \quad (17)$$

If $\beta < 1$ (under coupled):

$$\beta = \frac{1}{SWR(f_0)} \quad (18)$$

5.2.2 Impedance analysis and SWR

Initially, our objective was to determine whether the cavity was under-coupled or over-coupled. In order to assess this, we analyzed the Smith chart, as shown in Figure 56.

Figure 56: Smith chart in reflection. The cavity is under coupled

It is evident that the cavity is under-coupled. This information is crucial to consider before proceeding with the measurements. Knowing the coupling status is important for selecting the appropriate formulas, especially when calculating parameters such as the Standing Wave Ratio (SWR). The amplitude of the impedance as a function of ω ; ($|Z(\omega)|$) is shown in Figure 57.

Figure 57: Amplitude of the impedance as a function f (left) of and Standing wave ratio as a function of f (right)

We obtained the following values: $f_0 = 1.911494GHz$, $Q_0 = 7917$, and $\beta =$

0.41. With these results, we can graphically represent the anticipated behavior and compare it with the experimental data.

Figure 58: Comparison with experimental data and the fitted ones for $|Z|$ (left) $\angle Z$ (right)

In Figure 58, a slight deviation from the theoretical points is observed only in the region distant from zero. The reason may be the fact that the $\angle S_{11}(f_0)$ is set at zero adding an offset from the instrument, so either the estimation of this number was not very accurate, or there is a little, but relevant, fluctuation in time.

By selecting a narrow frequency range centered around f_0 , we can utilize the linear approximation for the phase of Z . This approach can be observed in Figure 59, where a linear fit is performed. From this linear fit, we can extract the value of Q_0 .

Figure 59: Linear fit of $\angle S_{11}$ (left) and Comparison with experimental data and the fitted ones for $|S_{11}|$ (right)

Q_0 was determined as 7825.43(87), which accounts for a discrepancy of about 0.1% from the previous one. Using the obtained parameters, we can perform a fitting

of the expected behavior of $|S_{11}|$ and compare it with the experimentally observed behavior as shown in Figure 59. The data obtained from the experiment aligns with the theoretical predictions, indicating a strong agreement between the two.

5.2.3 Reflection parameter analysis

In this section, the phase, amplitude, and Smith chart are analyzed for the reflection parameter S_{11} . Initially, a linear fit is performed for the phase around f_0 , as shown in Figure 60, and Q_0 was determined as 7765.13(91). By performing a non-linear fit of the amplitude, all three parameters can be estimated from a single measurement. This can be observed in Figure 60. The results obtained from the fit are $Q_0 = 7889.6(68)$ and $\beta = 0.40513(47)$. To further validate our measurements, we can compare the expected Smith chart with the measured one. This allows us to visually assess the agreement between the predicted and observed data. The comparison plot is shown in Figure 61.

Figure 60: Linear fit of $\angle S_{11}$ (left) and Non linear fit of $|S_{11}|$ with an under coupled mode (right)

Figure 61: Expected and measured Smith chart

Summary table

Procedure	Q_0	β
$ Z(\omega) $	7917.2	-
From SWR	-	0.4065
lin fit $\angle Z$	7825.43(87)	-
lin fit $\angle S_{11}$	7765.13(91)	-
Non lin fit $ S_{11} $	7.889.6(68)	0.40513(47)

Table 6: Procedures and values for Q_0 and β

5.2.4 A higher order, over coupled mode, TM120

In this section, we repeat the same procedure for the mode TM120, without the phase analysis, $f_0 = 5.576648GHz$. (See Figure 62).

Figure 62: Smith chart TM120 (top left), Theory and experiment comparison, over coupled mode (top right) and non-linear fit on reflection parameter (down)

Procedure	Q_0	β
$ Z(\omega) $	12152	-
From SWR	-	5.65
Non lin fit $ S_{11} $	12592.54(76)	5.94316(43)

Table 7: Procedures and values for Q_0 and β

5.3 Combined transmission and reflection

Reflection measurements are utilized to determine β_1 , β_2 , and Q_0 using the impedance, standing wave ratio calculations, and non-linear fitting of $|S_{11}|$. By obtaining Q_t from $|S_{12}|$, we can then measure Q_0 . This process has been carried out in three distinct modes. This part is done with a different pillbox cavity.

5.3.1 TM_{010} Mode

The resonant frequency of this mode is recorded as 1.9114994 GHz. Table 8 presents the summary for the reflection measurements. There is little fluctuation from the previous one due to the reproducibility of the environment. Here β_i is taken also from the impedance thanks to the value on the peak. Based on the information obtained from the Smith charts, it can be concluded that both β_2 and β_1 are less than one. See Figures 61 and 63.

Figure 63: Smith chart for the second port for the TM_{010} mode corresponding to β_2

Procedure	Q_{01}	Q_{02}	β_1	β_2
$ Z(\omega) $	7917.2	7896.4	0.410	0.0910
From SWR	-	-	0.4065	0.0910
Non lin fit $ S_{11} $	7889.6(68)	7903.5(84)	0.405137(47)	0.091013(63)

Table 8: Reflection measurements for TM_{010}

The transmission measurements yielded a value of $Q_t = 5309$, and by using the β values obtained from the standing wave ratio, a value of $Q_0 = 7899$ was obtained. From these values, we can plot a comparison between theory and data.

Figure 64: Theoretical and experimental curves for $|S_{12}|$ for the TM_{010} mode

Figure 65: Theoretical and experimental curves for $\angle S_{12}$ for the TM_{010} mode

5.3.2 TM_{110} Mode

The mode is located at a frequency of $f_0 = 3.046329GHz$. Table 9 presents the summary for the reflection measurements.

	Q_{01}	Q_{02}	β_1	β_2
$ Z(\omega) $	9713.2	8857.3	0.1752	0.0442
From SWR	-	-	0.1751	0.0441
Non lin fit $ S_{11} $	9454(21)	8648(53)	0.405137(47)	0.091013(63)

Table 9: Reflection measurements for TM_{110}

Figure 66: Smith chart for the first port for the TM_{110} mode corresponding to β_1

Figure 67: Smith chart for the second port for the TM_{110} mode corresponding to β_2

From transmission and SWR: $Q_t = 8259.8$, $Q_0 = 10070.3$.

Figure 68: Theoretical and experimental curves for $|S_{12}|$ for the TM_{110} mode

Figure 69: Theoretical and experimental curves for $\angle S_{12}$ for the TM_{110} mode

5.3.3 TM_{020} Mode

The mode is located at a frequency of $f_0 = 4.383681GHz$. Table 10 presents the summary for the reflection measurements.

Procedure	Q_{01}	Q_{02}	β_1	β_2
$ Z(\omega) $	10786	10493	6.601	1.057
From SWR	-	-	6.62	1.058
Non lin fit $ S_{11} $	11165(35)	10604(35)	6.678(16)	1.05951(99)

Table 10: Reflection measurements for TM_{020}

Figure 70: Smith chart for the first port for the TM_{020} mode corresponding to β_1

Figure 71: Smith chart for the second port for the TM_{020} mode corresponding to β_2

The transmission measurements and SWR resulted in: $Q_t = 1246.5$, $Q_0 = 10794$.

Figure 72: Theoretical and experimental curves for $|S_{12}|$ for the TM_{020} mode

Figure 73: Theoretical and experimental curves for $\angle S_{12}$ for the TM_{020} mode

5.3.4 TM_{211} Mode

The mode is located at a frequency of $f_0 = 5.500206GHz$. Table 11 presents the summary for the reflection measurements.

Procedure	Q_{01}	Q_{02}	β_1	β_2
$ Z(\omega) $	2476	1170	3.364	0.237
SWR	-	-	3.360	0.231
Non lin fit $ S_{11} $	2564(80)	1146.3(3.0)	3.477(12)	0.21851(35)

Table 11: Reflection measurements for TM_{211}

Figure 74: Smith chart for the first port for the TM_{211} mode corresponding to β_1

Figure 75: Smith chart for the second port for the TM_{211} mode corresponding to β_2

The resonant frequency was found to undergo a shift as a consequence of one port being over-coupled while the other port was under-coupled. This observation highlights the influence of disparate coupling conditions.

Figure 76: The behavior of impedance with Port 2 is open (red) and matched (blue) for the TM_{211} mode.

The inclusion of a matched load simulates the presence of an additional cable connected to port 2. According to our model, the resonant frequency should remain unaffected. However, the observed shift in the plot clearly indicates that the model fails to accurately describe the behavior of the TM_{211} mode. (See Figure 76).

6 Monitoring routine of f_0 and Q_l

As said before, the main source of errors is reproducibility. We analyzed the resonance frequency and Q_0 variation with respect to time for TM_{010} mode. A routine was developed by us to measure the resonant frequency and the quality factor during the whole night (starting from 1900h to 0900h the next day).

Figure 77: Resonant frequency

Figure 78: Quality factor

Figure 77 shows a shift in the resonance frequency. This process is mainly due to temperature variation, which slightly changes the shape of the cavity. While the oscillating behavior for Q_0 can be explained with variation in the environment and instability of the routine.

7 Frequency tuning in RF cavities

We demonstrated the operational principles of Slater’s theorem by observing changes in the resonance frequency of a pillbox cavity when its geometry is slightly modified. The modifications involve the insertion of two screws—one in the region dominated by the electric field and the other in the region dominated by the magnetic field.

7.1 Slater’s theorem

As expected, a small modification in the cavity’s geometry leads to a corresponding shift in the resonance frequency. In our specific case, where the variation is negligible compared to the total volume, we can simplify the theorem to the following equation, denoted as Equation 19.

$$\frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega} \simeq \frac{1}{W_{tot}} \left(\int_{\Delta V} \mu |H|^2 dv - \int_{\Delta V} \epsilon |E|^2 dV \right) \quad (19)$$

We anticipate that the frequency will increase when a volume perturbation ΔV is inserted in the region dominated by the magnetic field, and vice versa for the region dominated by the electric field. To achieve this, one screw is positioned longitudinally near the axis (A), while the other screw is placed along the lateral border (B). It is essential to note that this approach is applicable only when characterizing TM modes, as we have done since these modes are employed for particle acceleration.

Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that this method can also be utilized to estimate the accelerating field.

7.2 Measurement process

The experimental procedure involved selecting a mode and determining the initial positions of the screws, β_1 , β_2 , and Q_0 . These values were obtained by performing a non-linear fit on the reflection parameter. The quantity Q_l was derived from the bandwidth and resonant frequency of the transmission parameter.

Next, one of the screws was moved by 2 mm inside the cavity, and the measurements were repeated for this new configuration. This process was repeated for six different points, and then the first screw was returned to its original position while the other screw was moved, iterating the procedure. The analysis focused on the following modes: TM_{010} , TM_{110} , TM_{020} , and TM_{211} .

7.2.1 TM_{010} Mode

Table 12 presents the obtained data while altering the positions of Screw B and Screw A respectively.

Screw B (left) Screw A (right)

L(mm)	f_0 (GHz)	Q_0	Q_l	β_1	β_2
16	1.9115655	7881.5(91)	5300	0.4071(54)	0.08612(32)
14	1.9115914	7883.7(57)	5311	0.4011(34)	0.08659(21)
12	1.9116610	7805.3(49)	5331	0.4024(67)	0.08643(47)
10	1.9120284	7813.9(23)	5358	0.3964(36)	0.08516(28)
8	1.9122231	7793.7(89)	5363	0.3971(46)	0.08531(56)
6	1.9127036	7727.9(76)	5498	0.3926(53)	0.08432(32)

L(mm)	f_0 (GHz)	Q_0	Q_l	β_1	β_2
16	1.91153660	7914.1(91)	5343	0.4074(44)	0.08812(43)
14	1.9108496	7864.4(57)	5256	0.4035(67)	0.08634(51)
12	1.9084923	7308.8(49)	5212	0.3604(17)	0.06811(21)
10	1.9054213	7762.1(23)	5301	0.37965(12)	0.08456(32)
8	1.8990107	7701.7(89)	5245	0.3601(23)	0.082476(37)
6	1.8876287	7470.7(89)	5230	0.3298(11)	0.07851(29)

Table 12: Obtained data by altering the position of the Screw A for TM_{010} mode

During the experiments, it was observed that the frequency displacement was on the order of a few MHz. As anticipated, when screw B was moved, the frequency increased, while when screw A was moved, the frequency decreased.

Figure 79: Decrease in frequency due to movement of screw A for TM_{010} mode

Figure 80: Increase in frequency due to movement of screw B for TM_{010} mode

7.2.2 TM_{110} Mode

Table 13 presents the obtained data while altering the positions of Screw B and Screw A respectively.

Screw B (left) Screw A (right)

L(mm)	$f_0(GHz)$	Q_0	Q_l	β_1	β_2
16	3.0463312	8857.1(27)	7271	0.1805(23)	0.04421(93)
14	3.0469028	8810.9(34)	7365	0.1796(24)	0.04345(81)
12	3.0472528	9412.3(45)	7312	0.1873(56)	0.04536(69)
10	3.0478091	9331(38)	7430	0.1825(45)	0.04476(76)
8	3.0483841	9061(19)	7380	0.1823(47)	0.04356(90)
6	3.0491497	9286.8(75)	7401	0.1876(31)	0.0498(10)

L(mm)	$f_0(GHz)$	Q_0	Q_l	β_1	β_2
16	3.0461053	9746.4(25)	7301	0.1944(32)	0.04143(37)
14	3.0451591	9805.1(34)	7293	0.1939(43)	0.04059(23)
12	3.0436554	9829.6(51)	7287	0.1946(25)	0.04143(29)
10	3.040243	9537.9(18)	7261	0.1953(19)	0.03959(24)
8	3.02181184	9137.4(67)	7212	0.1975(46)	0.04012(76)
6	2.9855282	77545.3(56)	4702	0.1851(51)	0.04181(34)

Table 13: Obtained data by altering the position of the Screw A for TM_{110} mode

Furthermore, the behavior of this mode also aligns with the prediction. The observed frequency displacements and the corresponding effects of screw movements are consistent with the theoretical expectations.

7.2.3 TM_{020} Mode

Table 14 presents the obtained data while altering the positions of Screw B and Screw A respectively.

Screw B(left) Screw A(right)

L(mm)	$f_0(GHz)$	Q_0	Q_l	β_1	β_2
16	4.3841538	10591(99)	1201	6.612(93)	1.012(12)
14	4.3844694	10149(83)	1251	6.678(81)	1.023(15)
12	4.3853079	11256(98)	1209	6.641(69)	1.098(34)
10	4.3854350	10384(78)	1357	7.432(76)	1.041(67)
8	4.3855913	11361(85)	1162	7.398(90)	1.034(25)
6	4.3877975	12009(90)	1893	3.245(23)	2.456(10)

L(mm)	$f_0(GHz)$	Q_0	Q_l	β_1	β_2
16	4.3847085	16490(34)	1772	6.871(54)	1.056(14)
14	4.3840507	15019(54)	1701	7.677(67)	1.033(23)
12	4.3830183	12236(67)	1154	7.038(88)	1.307(26)
10	4.3828023	11143(81)	1289	6.798(45)	1.109(21)
8	4.380624	9994.6(44)	1134	6.373(78)	1.318(19)
6	4.3770184	9820(58)	1154	6.171(65)	1.437(15)

Table 14: Obtained data by altering the position of the Screw A for TM_{020} mode

As we explore this mode further, we begin to observe deviations from our model. Specifically, we notice significant jumps in the Q factor, both loaded and unloaded, which are not always accompanied by substantial variations in β_1 and β_2 . This phenomenon becomes more pronounced in the subsequent mode. The cause of these deviations is attributed to effects that our current model cannot accurately predict, particularly when one antenna is strongly over-coupled. This effect is amplified when the other antenna is under-coupled.

7.2.4 TM_{211} Mode

Screw B(left) Screw A(right)

L(mm)	$f_0(GHz)$	Q_0	Q_l	β_1	β_2
16	5.292796	503.4(12)	121	3.856(54)	0.0612(65)
14	5.292387	487.9(32)	115	3.879(29)	0.0601(39)
12	5.291853	362.1(16)	77	3.900(88)	0.0408(45)
10	5.290169	343.5(21)	72	3.814(67)	0.0372(32)
8	5.289465	481.7(10)	131	3.221(72)	0.0564(66)
6	5.281840	610.6(32)	204	2.003(53)	0.0411(71)

L(mm)	$f_0(GHz)$	Q_0	Q_l	β_1	β_2
16	5.292069	503.5(56)	124	3.856(23)	0.07131(23)
14	5.293813	2926(12)	576	4.123(65)	0.1202(65)
12	5.293207	2854(54)	568	4.021(41)	0.1312(61)
10	5.291198	2769(34)	554	3.908(32)	0.1344(54)
8	5.284565	2750(24)	602	3.456(66)	0.1712(12)
6	5.280316	2549(68)	421	5.128(26)	0.2041(39)

Table 15: Obtained data by altering the position of the Screw A for TM_{211} mode

As mentioned earlier, the observed behavior of the resonant frequency in this mode deviates from what would be expected based on our current understanding. The data from screw B suggests that this may not be a typical transverse magnetic (TM) mode. However, this alone does not provide a complete explanation for the behavior observed with screw A, where the frequency initially increases and then returns to its original state.

8 Multi cell cavity, an actual accelerating device

Figure 81: Multicell cavity

In this section, we showcase the results obtained from the measurement of a multicell cavity. Since it is made by more pillbox cavities together, for every configuration of the field inside, we expect to see one mode for each cavity in a small interval of frequency. Small with respect to the resonant frequency of another configuration of the field. The accelerating mode will be the critical coupled mode ($\beta = 1$), in which the cavity consists of two ports: port 1 serves as the power input, while Port 2 is utilized for signal monitoring. Our initial step involves identifying the accelerating mode of the cavity.

Figure 82: S_{11} Measurement multi-cell (left), S_{21} Measurement multi-cell (right)

We have a resonance for each single cavity, the accelerating mode is the one that is critical coupled with port 1. We found it at $f_0 = 11.423123GHz$. In order to find it we used reflection measurements (while keeping the other port open), and performed the nonlinear fit, obtaining $Q_0 = 6213.2(51)$ and $\beta_1 = 1.00123(71)$.

Figure 83: Critically coupled mode.

Methods	Linear fit of $\angle S_{11}$	Reflection $S_{11}(f)$	Non-linear fit
Q_0	5857.9 ± 4.6	6262.5	6213.2 ± 5.1
β	1	1	1.00123 ± 0.00071

Table 16: Accelerating mode - Reflection $S_{11}(f)$ measurements : $f_0 = 11.423$ GHz

We analyzed also the transmission parameter $|S_{21}|$ and got $Q_l = 3114$ from the bandwidth analysis

8.0.1 Other operating modes

Two additional modes are present in the multicell cavity. Figure 84 shows that for the first mode, the unloaded Q_0 factor is 1471 and the β value is 0.383. On the other hand, Figure 85 displays the second mode, with an unloaded Q_0 factor of 2378 and a β value of 0.846.

Figure 84: Other operating modes: 1.

Figure 85: Other operating modes: 2.

8.1 Comparison of accelerating mode and close mode frequencies

Figures 86 and 87 reveal a noticeable frequency difference between the accelerating modes and the nearest adjacent modes. This frequency difference is approximately 4.4GHz.

Figure 86: Accelerating modes.

Figure 87: First closest modes.

9 Conclusions

In this study, our emphasis was placed on describing the properties of accelerating devices that are frequently utilized in contemporary particle accelerators. These devices operate at higher frequencies, typically within the gigahertz (GHz) range.

We gained an understanding of the physical significance behind the measurements obtained from the vector network analyzer and effectively established connections to derive other relevant quantities. After examining the strip-line Beam Position Meter (BPM), it became evident that the signals within the distinct strips are indeed adequately separated from one another, as anticipated.

The pillbox cavity was examined by its transmission, reflection, and combined transmission-reflection measurements using different techniques and different fits. Theoretically expected behaviors were observed for almost all quantities for all the investigated modes of the cavity. Being under-coupled or over-coupled was found to be an important factor in obtaining accurate results. Following the results of combined measurements of transmission and reflection, the influence of disparate coupling conditions was noted. The resonant frequency was found to undergo a shift as a consequence of one port being over-coupled while the other port was under-coupled.

Developing a routine capable of continuously tracking a cavity's resonant frequency and quality factor for a user-defined duration (such as overnight in our context), led us to the conclusion that these properties are primarily influenced by temperature.

The operational concepts of Slater's theorem were demonstrated through modifications to the pillbox cavity's geometry, achieved by introducing screws in two specific regions—one governed by the electric field and the other by the magnetic field dominance. For higher orders, discrepancies from the existing model (according to Slater's theorem) were observed. These deviations were linked to effects beyond the accurate prediction of our current model, particularly when one antenna experiences significant over-coupling.

Through the process of analyzing the multicell cavity, comprised of numerous interconnected pillbox cavities, a significant frequency difference between the accelerating modes and the closest neighboring modes was identified.